

Increased Picture-Word Interference in Chronic and Recreational Users of Cocaine

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Abstract

Objective

Language production requires that speakers effectively recruit inhibitory control to successfully produce speech. The use of cocaine is associated with impairments in cognitive control processes in the nonverbal domain, but little is known about the impact of cocaine abuse on these processes during language production. This study aims to observe the possible impairment of inhibitory control in language production among chronic cocaine polydrug users in rehabilitation and recreational cocaine users.

Method

Two experiments were carried out on chronic cocaine users in rehabilitation (Experiment 1) and recreational cocaine polydrug users (Experiment 2) performing a picture–word task, which provides an index of semantic interference. Participants were matched for sex, age, and intelligence (Raven’s progressive matrices) with cocaine-free controls, and their performance was compared on the picture–word task.

Results

Chronic and recreational users showed significantly larger semantic interference effects than cocaine-free controls, thereby indicating a deficit in the ability to inhibit interfering information.

Conclusions

These findings indicate a relationship between the consumption of cocaine, even at recreational levels, and the inhibitory processes that reduce the activation of the distractor’s prepotent lexical representation when the target picture and the distractor are semantically related. This deficit may be critical in adapting and responding to many real-life situations where an efficient self-monitoring system is necessary for the prevention of errors during speech production.

Increased Picture-Word Interference in Chronic and Recreational Users of Cocaine

Cocaine powder is one the most used illicit drugs worldwide. It is frequently used despite the fact that regular use has been associated with dependence and cardiovascular, neurological, and mental health problems (European Monitoring Centre for Drugs and Drug Addiction, 2015). The annual prevalence of cocaine use was estimated at around 0.4% of the global population aged 15–64 in 2014 (United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime, 2016). Although the prevalence of cocaine use is steady in Europe and it is declining in North America, consumption still remains at a high level and the markets are stable (United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime, 2016).

Previous researchers assessing neuropsychological functioning have examined the integrity of cognitive processes in chronic cocaine users, indicating that long-term cocaine users show several cognitive dysfunctions when compared with cocaine-free individuals (Goldstein et al., 2004; Jovanovski, Erb, & Zakzanis, 2005; Spronk, van Wel, Ramaekers, & Verkes, 2013; Woicik et al., 2008; see Spronk, 2013, for a recent review). The typical observed impairments include deficiencies in cognitive flexibility (Verdejo-García & Pérez-García, 2007), episodic memory (Reske, Eidt, Delis, & Paulus, 2010; Vonmoos et al., 2013), social and nonsocial decision making (Hulka et al., 2014), prosodic and cross-modal emotion processing (Hulka et al., 2013), attention switching (Kübler, Murphy, & Garavan, 2005), and decision making. There appears to be a particularly strong link between cocaine use and impairments in the ability to stop predominant responses or suppress irrelevant information, a skill usually termed as *inhibitory control* (Fillmore & Rush, 2002; Morie, De Sanctis, Garavan, & Foxe, 2014; Morein-Zamir, Jones, Bullmore, Robbins, & Ersche, 2015; Spronk, De Bruijn, van Wel, Ramaekers, & Verkes, 2015). Supporting the susceptibility of inhibitory control to cocaine use, a recent study showed deficits in response inhibition for cocaine-using

Picture-word interference and cocaine use 4

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2 individuals that were, however, preserved by intensive inhibitory control training, which
3 might support treatment outcomes via better behavioral inhibition (Alcorn, Pike, Stoops,
4 Lile, & Rush, 2017).
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9 The frontostriatal circuitry is proposed as the neural substrate of inhibitory
10 control (Bari & Robbins, 2013; Miller & Cohen, 2001) and dopamine as the
11 neurotransmitter targeted by cocaine (Hershey et al., 2004), playing an important
12 neuromodulatory role (Arnsten, Wang, & Paspalas, 2012; Robbins & Arnsten, 2009).
13 Previous investigations of inhibitory control in cocaine addicts have shown reduced
14 prefrontal activity relative to controls when performing tasks tapping conflict resolution
15 and inhibitory control (e.g., GO-NOGO, Stop-Signal, Stroop; for a review see
16 Goldstein & Volkow, 2011). Thus, inhibition has been highlighted as one of the
17 processes with a relevant impairment in stimulant abusers (Bolla, Cadet, & London,
18 1998; Ersche et al., 2011; Fillmore & Rush, 2002; Morein-Zamir & Robbins, 2015).
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31 In this sense, to the extent that inhibitory processes are also involved in language
32 production, we would expect to find observable deficits in language production in
33 cocaine abusers. Thus, in our studies we assessed language-related processes in cocaine
34 abusers. However, in understanding the transition from recreational drug use to
35 addiction, focus on recreational users is also needed (Bosker et al., 2017). Indeed, recent
36 studies have indicated that there is an increasing population that does not meet the
37 criteria for abuse or dependence but preferentially take cocaine on a monthly basis (1–4
38 grams per month) along with other substances of abuse (e.g., 3,4-
39 Methylenedioxymethamphetamine [MDMA], alcohol, and cannabis). This population
40 shows types of cognitive impairments similar to chronic cocaine users. In this regard,
41 recreational cocaine users show impaired performance on tasks tapping into response
42 inhibition, but not response execution and inhibition of return (Colzato & Hommel,
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2009; Colzato, van den Wildenberg, & Hommel, 2007), sustained attention and attentional shifting (Hulka et al., 2013; Soar, Mason, Potton, & Dawkins, 2012), latent inhibition (Soar, Dawkins, Page, & Wooldridge, 2015), and the emergence and resolution of response conflict (Sellaro, Hommel, & Colzato, 2013). For this reason, recreational users were also included in our studies

To date, much research has sought to clarify the relationship between drug abuse and inhibitory control using selective attention and action control tasks (see Bardo, Fishbein, Milich, & more, 2011), and very little research has been directed to study the inhibitory processes engaged in language production. Ruiz et al. (2015) reported that chronic and recreational cocaine users, compared to cocaine-free controls, exhibit longer naming latencies measured through a block-cycled semantic task, assumed to indicate a vulnerability to semantic interference; that is, they found exaggerated slower naming latencies to elements presented in a homogeneous semantic context in comparison with a heterogeneous semantic context. The tests employed in their study involved the process of rejecting the competitors in an unintentional manner. Semantic blocking produced interference by the continuous implicit activation of semantic competitor, however, the participants do not intentionally try to suppress the competition because they might not even be aware of it (Gordon & Cheimariou, 2013). In the present study, however, we aimed to extend and complement these findings by employing a rather different task in which the participants are required to engage in the effortful and intentional action of rejecting semantic interference produced by explicitly presented distracting information. To this end, we used the picture-word interference task (Rosinski, Golinkoff, & Kukish, 1975). In this task, participants are instructed to name pictures as quickly and accurately as possible, while ignoring a distractor word superimposed on the picture. The distractor word can be semantically related to the

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3 picture name (target: ship; distractor: train) or semantically unrelated (target: ship;
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5 distractor: chair). The typical result is slower naming latencies to semantically related
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7 target–distractor pairs in comparison with semantically unrelated pairs. This effect is
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9 known as the semantic interference effect (e.g., Glaser & Dünghoff, 1984). The origin
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11 of this effect is still a matter of debate. One account is that this interference effect arises
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13 during lemma selection due to competition among the activated lexical entries of the
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15 target and the coactivated lexical entries of the distractor by virtue of their semantic
16
17 relatedness (Levelt, 1999; Roelofs, 2003; Schriefers, Meyer, & Levelt, 1990). Another
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19 explanation is that the effect emerges later, during an articulatory buffering stage, when
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21 the written distractor word activates the associated articulatory program, which is
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23 entered into an output buffer. The process of removing the articulatory program for the
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25 distractor and inserting the target articulatory program is assumed to take longer when
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27 the distractor is semantically related to the target than when it is unrelated (e.g.,
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29 Finkbeiner & Caramazza, 2006). Both accounts assume that semantically related
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31 distractors generate more interference than the unrelated ones, and therefore it is
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33 expected that selective inhibition would overcome the tendency to respond to the word
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35 instead of the picture (Shao, Roelofs, Martin, & Meyer, 2015). Selective inhibition
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37 involves the top-down suppression of specific strong competitors to a response, which is
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39 induced by an external distractor. This is assumed to be selective because evidence
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41 suggests that it is specifically applied to the conditions of the picture–word task in
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43 which there are strongly competing responses (Shao, Meyer, & Roelofs, 2013; for
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45 nonlinguistic tasks see Nigg, 2000; Ridderinkhof, 2002). Further evidence supporting
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47 the idea that the picture–word task can reflect the ability to inhibit specific unwanted
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49 responses comes from neuropsychological studies. In particular, Biegler et al. (2008)
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51 observed an exaggerated semantic blocking effect by testing patients with damaged left
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3 inferior frontal gyrus, an area presumably engaged in the selection among semantic
4 competing representations (Thompson-Schill, 2003; Thompson-Schill, D'Esposito,
5 Aguirre, & Farah, 1997; Thompson-Schill et al., 2002).
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9 Along with the experiments presented in this study, we investigated whether
10 chronic use of cocaine (Experiment 1) and recreational use of cocaine (Experiment 2)
11 lead to deficits in the mechanism that underlies the inhibition of distraction information
12 in spoken word production. The aim of Experiment 1 was to examine whether chronic
13 cocaine users in rehabilitation, who were abstinent of any kind of other drugs (excepting
14 alcohol and tobacco), show less efficient suppression of distractor words so that their
15 presence slows down responding to the target pictures—provided that, we would expect
16 a higher picture–word Interference in chronic cocaine users in rehabilitation compared
17 to cocaine-free controls. In Experiment 2, based on recent research showing deficits in
18 inhibitory control in recreational cocaine users (Colzato & Hommel, 2009; Colzato et
19 al., 2007; Colzato, van den Wildenberg, & Hommel, 2009; Ruiz, Paolieri, Colzato, &
20 Bajo, 2015; Sellaro et al., 2013; Soar et al., 2012; Soar et al., 2015), we hypothesized
21 that smaller amounts of cocaine also lead users to show greater picture–word
22 interference effects as compared to cocaine-free controls. This pattern would suggest
23 that cocaine use, even with recreational purposes, produces inefficient inhibitory
24 processes at the lexical selection level.
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44 **General Methods**

45 **Procedure, Apparatus, and Stimuli**

46 The complete procedure lasted approximately 90 minutes and the participants
47 were tested individually. The session started by fulfilling a drug use questionnaire,
48 followed by a clinical and neuropsychiatric interview and the subsequent screening
49 tasks. Then, participants performed the picture–word task. This task consisted of 56 line
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3 drawings of common objects from the Snodgrass and Vanderwart (1980) corpus, which
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5 served as targets in this procedure.

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7 The pictures were combined with semantically related and unrelated words.
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9 Pictures and distractor words were selected to minimize overlap between initial
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11 phonemes of the names whilst the frequency, number of letters, number of phonemes,
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13 syllables, and gender were also controlled (Duchon, Perea, Sebastián-Gallés, Martí, &
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15 Carreiras, 2013). The pictures were enclosed in a virtual frame of 227×227 pixels on a
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17 computer screen and were presented on a white background in the center of a computer
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19 screen. Distractor words were superimposed on the center of the target picture. A total
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21 of 56 distractor words were used twice: once as a semantically related distractor for the
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23 one target picture and once as a semantically unrelated distractor. For example, for the
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25 picture of a ship, the semantically related distractor was “*train*,” and “*chair*” served as
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27 the semantically unrelated distractor. Four randomized presentations were scheduled
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29 using a Latin square design. Within a single presentation there were four blocks of 30
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31 picture–word trials. The four blocks were presented in an alternating sequence, with a
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33 pause after each block. Thus, the presentation contained 56 semantically related trials
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35 and 56 semantically unrelated trials, with an additional eight picture–word filler trials
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37 (total = 120 trials).
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41 We presented the stimuli on a computer screen, and an electronic device
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43 recorded verbal responses. The experimenter was instructed to record errors and
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45 equipment failures. At the beginning of the task, as a familiarization block, participants
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47 were shown the complete set of pictures and their corresponding names to familiarize
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49 themselves with the names of the pictures and to avoid using alternative names. After
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51 the familiarization phase, the participants received the four test blocks. For the test
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53 blocks, the participants were instructed to name aloud each picture as quickly and
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3 accurately as possible, avoiding naming the distractor word superimposed on the target
4 picture (Figure 1). On each trial a fixation cross appeared at the center of the screen for
5 500 milliseconds, followed by the stimulus that remained on the screen until the
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7 response or for a maximum of 3000 milliseconds, which was followed by a blank
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9 interval of 500 milliseconds. Response latencies were measured from the presentation
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11 of the stimulus to the onset of the response.
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16 In both Experiment 1 and Experiment 2, participants were matched for race, age,
17 and IQ (measured using the Raven's Standard Progressive Matrices; Raven, Court, &
18 Raven, 1988). In addition, participants performed a Boston naming test (Kaplan,
19 Goodglass, & Weintraub, 1983), a modified version of the verbal fluency test (VFT) for
20 native Spanish speakers from the screen for cognitive impairment in psychiatric patients
21 (SCIP; Pino et al., 2006) and the memory span test (Daneman & Carpenter, 1980) to
22 guarantee intact verbal and memory functions.
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31 Information regarding the recent use, amount, and patterns of alcohol and drug
32 consumption during the 6 months prior to the experiment was gathered through a self-
33 report questionnaire (cf. Colzato et al., 2007). Chronic cocaine users in rehabilitation
34 were screened for use of other drugs. The results of this screening showed that all
35 participants had only used cocaine except for one who had also used MDMA.
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37 Recreational cocaine users, on the other hand, reported sporadic use of other drugs such
38 as MDMA or cannabis, although they reported using cocaine much more frequently.
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40 Given that the recreational users were not "pure" cocaine users, this group of users was
41 called "recreational cocaine polydrug users." Following Colzato et al.'s (2004)
42 procedure, in order to assure the compliance of the participants with the instruction at
43 the beginning of the experiment saliva samples were required, although they were not
44 further analyzed. The study was approved by the university ethics committee. All
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3 participants provided written informed consent and were compensated for their
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5 participation.
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12 *Figure 1*

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15 **Statistical Analysis**

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17 Analyses were performed using IBM SPSS statistics 20. In both experiments, we
18 adopted a significance level of $p < .05$. Analyses of variance (ANOVAs) were used for
19 participants and items, yielding F_1 and F_2 statistics, respectively. These statistics are
20 usually used in the field of psycholinguistics to check whether the findings could be
21 generalizable not only across participants but also across similar stimulus material.
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25 Differences between the chronic cocaine users in rehabilitation group, the
26 recreational cocaine users, and cocaine-free controls in terms of age, IQ, alcohol
27 consumption, and neuropsychological screening tasks were analyzed using t -tests. We
28 carried out repeated ANOVA measures to compare response latencies and errors with
29 semantic relatedness (related and unrelated word distractors to target pictures) as a
30 within-subject factor and group (chronic cocaine users in abstinence or recreational
31 cocaine polydrug users vs. cocaine-free controls) as a between-subject factor. In
32 addition, to assess the picture–word interference effect we carried out Newman-Keuls
33 post hoc analyses. Moreover, partial correlations coefficients we obtained with a two-
34 fold aim: to test whether the cognitive impairment is proportional to the amount of
35 cocaine consumed by observing the relationship between relevant cocaine use variables
36 (e.g., lifetime amount, times per week of cocaine use, maximum peak in 12 hours, and
37 monthly consumed cocaine in grams) and cognitive performance on the picture–word
38 task and to control for the consumption of those drugs (alcohol, tobacco, and cannabis)
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3 that varied significantly between the cocaine groups and controls. Partial Eta squared
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5 (η^2_p) was calculated to assess effect sizes.

7 8 **Experiment 1**

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10 The first experiment included 40 adults (20 chronic cocaine users in rehabilitation
11 and 20 healthy and cocaine-free controls). Ten of the participants were recruited from a
12 previous study carried out by the same authors (Ruiz et al., 2015). Chronic cocaine
13 users in rehabilitation were recruited from a local rehabilitation center. Before their
14 participation in the rehabilitation program, chronic users had been taking cocaine on a
15 daily basis for several years ($M = 9.6$, $SD = 4.83$) administered by the snorting route.
16 Cocaine abstinence is a requirement for attending the rehabilitation program, and at the
17 moment of experimental testing, they had been cocaine abstinent for several months (M
18 $= 4.42$, $SD = 3.99$). Specific inclusion criteria for chronic cocaine users in rehabilitation
19 were (a) fulfilling the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders IV (DSM-
20 IV) criteria for cocaine dependence as assessed by the Structured Clinical Interview for
21 DSM-IV disorders (SCID; American Psychological Association, 2000)—Clinician
22 Version (First, Spitzer, Gibbon, & Williams, 1997) and (b) a minimum abstinence
23 interval of 30 days for all substances of abuse except tobacco, checked by periodic urine
24 toxicology tests, therapists, or self-reports. The exclusion criteria were (a) the presence
25 of any Axis I or Axis II disorders except substance abuse, determined by the Mini
26 International Neuropsychiatric Interview (MINI; Lecrubier et al., 1997), a brief
27 diagnostic tool that screens for several psychiatric disorders; (b) a history of brain injury
28 or central nervous system diseases; (c) an excessive intake of alcohol (>280 g/week for
29 men and >168g/week for women; Foster & Marriott, 2006). At the time of the
30 assessment, individuals in the rehabilitation program were free of psychiatric
31 prescription medication. The control participants were recruited via notes posted on
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public bulletin boards and by word of mouth. Additional exclusion criteria for the control subjects were any of the criteria for Axis I or Axis II psychiatric disorders, including substance abuse (except for tobacco) or clinically significant medical disease (e.g., multiple sclerosis).

Participants were also asked a number of questions regarding the use of substances during the 6 months prior to participation. The results of this interview indicated that four chronic cocaine users in rehabilitation and five cocaine-free users smoked marijuana, whereas one chronic cocaine user in rehabilitation reported having used MDMA (ecstasy). Chronic cocaine users were engaged in a detoxification program, and they were routinely (every 30 days) screened for drug use through urine analysis. We asked participants to refrain from taking all types of psychoactive drugs for at least two days before the testing session. All participants were asked to refrain from consuming alcohol the night before the experimental session and to have a normal night of rest.

Table 1

Results

Table 1 depicts descriptive statistics regarding the demographic composition of the groups and drug use. Alcohol-intake habit information was gathered through a self-report questionnaire inquiring about the participant's alcohol consumption expressed in standard "drinks" or "units," equal to 10 millimeters or 8 grams of pure alcohol (International Center for Alcohol, 2005). Chronic cocaine users in rehabilitation differed from controls in the amount of tobacco and alcohol used before they entered in the detoxification program, although they were abstinent once they engaged in the detoxification process.

Table 2

No significant group differences were obtained for IQ, $t(38) = 1.61, p = .11$; memory span test, $t(38) = 1.85, p = .071$; verbal fluency test, $t(38) = 1.66, p = .10$; and verbal functions on the Boston naming test, $t(38) = 0.20, p = .84$ (see Table 2). For the picture–word interference task, four types of response were excluded from the analysis (5.35%): (a) naming errors, hesitations, distractor naming, and microphone failures, and (b) responses longer than 2000 milliseconds or shorter than 250 milliseconds.

Response Latencies

The analysis showed a significant effect of group, $F_1(1, 38) = 5.06, p = .03, \eta_p^2 = .11$; $F_2(1, 110) = 39.16, p < .001, \eta_p^2 = .26$, showing that chronic cocaine users needed more time to name the stimuli ($M = 930, SD = 121$) than the cocaine-free control group ($M = 848, SD = 117$). A significant effect of semantic relatedness, $F_1(1, 38) = 60.23, p < .001, \eta_p^2 = 0.61$; $F_2(1, 110) = 27.10, p < .001, \eta_p^2 = 0.19$, indicated that the semantically related condition led to longer naming latencies ($M = 912, SD = 133$) than the semantically unrelated condition ($M = 867, SD = 114$). Most importantly, the semantic relatedness \times group interaction was significant, $F_1(1, 38) = 13.12, p < .001, \eta_p^2 = .25$; $F_2(1, 110) = 7.29, p = .008, \eta_p^2 = .06$, indicating that chronic cocaine users displayed a larger semantic interference effect than the cocaine-free controls. Post hoc Newman-Keuls analyses showed a reliable difference between the semantically unrelated and the semantically related condition for the group of chronic users (65 ms.; $p < .001$) and the cocaine-free group (23 ms.; $p < .01$; Figure 2).

Figure 2

Errors

In both analyses there was no effect of group, semantic relatedness, or an interaction between these two factors (all $ps > .05$).

Correlations

We computed partial correlation coefficients to test whether the magnitude of the picture–word interference effect was proportional to the amount of cocaine consumed. These coefficients included partial correlations between relevant cocaine use variables (e.g., lifetime amount, times per week of cocaine use, maximum peak in 12 h, and weekly cocaine consumption in grams) and both the picture–word interference effect (the result of the subtraction between semantically related and semantically unrelated response latencies) and errors when controlling for the use of other drugs (tobacco, alcohol, MDMA, and cannabis). The picture–word effect correlated positively with times per week of cocaine use ($r = 0.524$; $p = 0.03$; Figure 3) and the amount of cocaine used in a week ($r = .618$; $p = .01$; Figure 4). Thus, it appears that heavy cocaine use (more times and a higher amount per week) may impair performance on the picture–word task. No other correlations were found ($p > 0.05$).

Discussion

The aim of Experiment 1 was to examine impaired inhibitory processes in the verbal domain in chronic cocaine users in rehabilitation compared to cocaine-free controls. Both groups showed similar performance when naming target pictures in the semantically unrelated condition, but chronic cocaine users showed more pronounced picture–word effects when the target picture and the distracting word were semantically related. Additionally, partial correlations indicated that heavy cocaine use (more times per week and higher amounts per week) seems to contribute to the greater picture–word interference effect.

These results, together with the assumption of impaired inhibitory processes in long-term cocaine users (Ersche et al., 2012; Fillmore & Rush, 2002; Goldstein & Volkow, 2002; Rosselli, Ardila, Lubomski, Murray, & King, 2001; Volkow et al.,

2010), lead us to consider that the greater picture–word interference reflects a deficit in the inhibitory mechanism involved in the interference control of distracting information during lexical selection. In order to assess whether other cocaine users—who do not qualify as chronic cocaine users but often consume cocaine for recreational purposes—would also show exaggerated naming latencies when target pictures and distractor words are semantically related, we conducted another experiment with the same materials and procedure as Experiment 1, but testing recreational cocaine polydrug users.

Figure 3 and 4

Experiment 2

The second experiment included 40 adults (20 recreational cocaine users and 20 healthy and cocaine naïve controls). Six of the participants in Experiment 2 were recruited from a previous study carried out by the same authors (Ruiz et al., 2015). These constituted both the recreational cocaine polydrug users and cocaine-free controls. We recruited the participants via notes posted on community bulletin boards and by word of mouth. Specific inclusion criteria for recreational cocaine polydrug users were: (a) a monthly consumption of between 1 and 4 grams by snorting for a minimum of two years; (b) no Axis I or Axis II psychiatric disorders (DSM-IV; American Psychological Association 2000), including substance abuse (except tobacco); (c) no clinically significant medical disease; and (d) no use of prescription medication. Cocaine-free controls met the same criteria, but without reporting a history of past or current cocaine use.

Participants were selected from a pool of 50 potential volunteers who responded to the advertisements. They underwent a telephone interview using the MINI (Lecrubier

et al., 1997), a brief diagnostic tool that screens for several psychiatric disorders. Within this pool of potential participants, meeting psychiatric disorders (psychotic symptoms, anxiety, and depression), alcohol abuse, or medication were the most common exclusion criteria. Furthermore, all participants performed a set of screening tasks identical to Experiment 1. Moreover, we asked them to refrain from taking all types of psychoactive drugs for at least two days before the testing session. All participants were asked to refrain from consuming alcohol the night before the experimental session and to have a normal night of rest.

In the 6 months prior to participation, thirteen recreational cocaine polydrug users and three cocaine-free controls smoked cannabis whereas 15 recreational users reported having used MDMA (ecstasy) and eight reported having used ketamine. Although recreational cocaine polydrug users report using several drugs of abuse, they stated their preference for cocaine as the main stimulant drug of choice.

Results

Recreational cocaine polydrug users differ from control in the amount of tobacco, alcohol and cannabis used in the last 6 months prior to the testing session (Table 1). No significant group differences were obtained for IQ, $t(38) = -0.17, p = .85$; memory span test, $t(38) = 1.44, p = .15$; verbal fluency test, $t(38) = 0.82, p = .41$; and verbal functions in the Boston naming test, $t(38) = -0.22, p = .82$ (see Table 2). Following the same response exclusion criteria as Experiment 1, 6% of the total responses were excluded from the analysis.

Response Latencies

The analysis of response latencies showed a significant effect of group only in the item analysis, $F_1(1, 38) = 2.9, p = .10, \eta_p^2 = .07$; $F_2(1, 110) = 18.3, p < .001, \eta_p^2 = .14$, showing that recreational cocaine polydrug users were slower in naming the stimuli

($M = 846$, $SD = 80$) than the cocaine-free control group ($M = 796$, $SD = 73$). A significant effect of semantic relatedness, $F_1(1, 38) = 94.73$, $p < .001$, $\eta_p^2 = .71$; $F_2(1, 110) = 33.02$, $p < .001$, $\eta_p^2 = .23$, indicated that the semantically related condition led to longer naming latencies ($M = 843$, $SD = 101$) than the semantically unrelated condition ($M = 796$, $SD = 92$). Most importantly, the semantic relatedness \times group interaction was significant, $F_1(1, 38) = 22.94$, $p < .001$, $\eta_p^2 = .37$; $F_2(1, 110) = 9.37$, $p = .002$, $\eta_p^2 = .08$, indicating that recreational cocaine polydrug users showed greater semantic interference effects than the cocaine-free controls. Post hoc Newman-Keuls analyses revealed a reliable difference between the semantically unrelated and the semantically related condition for the group of recreational cocaine polydrug users (70 ms.; $p < .001$) and the cocaine-free group (23 ms.; $p < .01$; Figure 5).

Figure 5

Errors

A significant main effect of group, $F_1(1, 38) = 5.50$, $p = .024$, $\eta_p^2 = .37$; $F_2(1, 110) = 4.85$, $p = .03$, $\eta_p^2 = .58$, revealed that the recreational cocaine polydrug users committed more errors ($M = 2.98$, $SD = 1.95$) than the control group ($M = 2.07$, $SD = 1.38$). Neither the main effect of semantic relatedness nor the semantic relatedness \times group interaction were significant, $F_s < 1$.

Correlations

As in Experiment 1, we computed partial correlation coefficients to test whether the magnitude of the picture–word interference effect was proportional to the amount of cocaine consumed. These coefficients included partial correlations between relevant cocaine use variables (e.g., lifetime amount, times per week of cocaine use, maximum peak in 12 h, and weekly cocaine consumption in grams) and both the picture-word interference effect and errors when controlling for the use of other drugs (tobacco,

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2 alcohol, MDMA, and cannabis). The picture-word effect correlated positively with
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4 times per month of cocaine use ($r = 0.651$; $p = .006$). Thus, it appears that heavy
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6 cocaine use (more times per month) may impair performance on the picture-word task
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8 (Figure 6). No other correlations were found ($p > .05$).
9
10

11 *Figure 6*
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14 **Discussion**

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16 As expected, the group of recreational cocaine users showed similar patterns of
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18 performance when naming target pictures with superimposed distractor words compared
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20 to the chronic group of Experiment 1. However, they differ when compared with
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22 cocaine-free controls, so that recreational cocaine polydrug users showed longer naming
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24 latencies for the target pictures in the presence of a semantically related distractor word
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26 than the controls. The results for Experiment 2 are in accord with those studies in which
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28 recreational cocaine users manifest an impaired performance on tasks tapping inhibition
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30 (Colzato & Hommel, 2009; Colzato et al., 2007; Ruiz et al., 2015; Sellaro et al., 2013;
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32 Soar et al., 2015; Soar et al., 2012; Vonmoos et al., 2013). Thus, these results taken
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34 together suggest that even the consumption of small amounts of cocaine may lead to
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36 inefficient control of interference in lexical selection during language production.
37
38 However, it is important to note that the causal role of drug use must be taken with
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40 caution because the recreational cocaine polydrug users used more tobacco, alcohol, and
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42 other drugs than the control group. In addition, it is important to be aware that
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44 preexistent endophenotypes that are known to contribute to behavioral performance may
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46 have a role to play in the impairment of the interference control mechanism in lexical
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48 selection during language production in recreational users (Ersche et al., 2012; Verdejo-
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50 García, Lawrence, & Clark, 2008).
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55 *Figure 2*
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General Discussion

In experiments 1 and 2, we report for the first time a detectable impairment in interference control in lexical selection during language production for chronic (Experiment 1) and recreational (Experiment 2) cocaine consumers. Both chronic cocaine users in rehabilitation and recreational cocaine users showed an exaggerated semantic interference effect during the naming of target with semantically related distractors relative to the cocaine-free control group. The semantic interference effect can be explained in terms of lemma selection due to the competition among the activated lexical entries of the target and the coactivated lexical entries of the distractor by virtue of their semantic relatedness (Levelt, 1999; Roelofs, 2003; Schriefers et al., 1990) or by a process of removing a previously activated articulatory program that entered into an output buffer and is assumed to take longer when the distractor is semantically related to the target (Finkbeiner & Caramazza, 2006; Mahon, Costa, Peterson, Vargas, & Caramazza, 2007). Both accounts assume that semantically related distractors generate more interference than unrelated distractors, and thus it would be expected that inhibition plays a role in selectively suppressing specific strong competitors to a response. Thus, inhibition is assumed to be selective because the evidence suggests that it is specifically applied to the conditions of the picture-word task in which there are strongly competing responses (Shao et al., 2013; Shao et al., 2015).

The present study adds to previous studies in inhibition language-related impairments (Ruiz et al., 2015) by showing impaired interference control in a task where the distractors are overtly present and the participants are explicitly instructed to avoid them. In the study by Ruiz et al. (2015), cocaine users showed impaired inhibition when testing them in a blocked picture-naming task where strongly competing

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2
3 responses were activated in the absence of overt distracting information. The results of
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5 the present study and those by Ruiz et al. (2015) suggest that the ability of cocaine users
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7 to cope with semantic interference seems to be similarly impaired in conditions where
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9 distractors are either explicitly or implicitly presented. The results of both studies fit in
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11 well with the observation of Shao et al. (2015), suggesting that the underlying deficits
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13 of inhibitory mechanisms may be similar for the two groups. Several
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15 neuropsychological studies with frontally damaged patients have supported the idea that
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17 semantic interference paradigms can reflect an impaired ability to inhibit specific
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19 unwanted responses (Biegler, Crowther, & Martin, 2008; Piai, Riès, & Swick, 2016).
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21 These studies suggest that left frontal areas are involved in the selection of the lexical
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23 target among semantically competing representations (Thompson-Schill, 2003;
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25 Thompson-Schill, D'Esposito, Aguirre, & Farah, 1997; Thompson-Schill et al., 2002).
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27 Therefore, we propose that the chronic and recreational cocaine users may suffer from
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29 similar deficits, although in a more moderate form. These findings are compatible with
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31 those from other investigations that support the impairment of inhibitory processes in
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33 chronic and recreational cocaine users in the nonverbal domain (Colzato & Hommel,
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35 2009; Colzato et al., 2007; Ersche et al., 2012; Fillmore & Rush, 2002; Goldstein &
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37 Volkow, 2002; Rosselli et al., 2001; Sellaro et al., 2013; Verdejo-García, Perales, &
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39 Pérez-García, 2007; Volkow et al., 2010).

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44 In experiments 1 and 2, the cocaine-free control groups replicated the typical
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46 picture-word effect observed in seminal studies (e.g., Glaser & Dünghoff, 1984),
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48 showing an increase in the naming latencies when the target picture was semantically
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50 related to the distractor word in comparison with the condition in which the target
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52 picture and the distractor word were semantically unrelated. In Experiment 1, chronic
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54 cocaine users in rehabilitation showed an exaggerated picture-word effect, which was
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3 also evident in Experiment 2 in recreational cocaine polydrug users. The observed
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5 results led us to consider that cocaine use is related to a deficit in inhibition, including
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7 distractor inhibition in naming. Moreover, the finding of the exaggerated picture-word
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9 effect in recreational cocaine polydrug users leads us to speculate that the consumption
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11 of small amounts of cocaine results in poorer naming performance due to the ineffective
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13 triggering of the inhibitory mechanism. The apparent link between cocaine abuse and
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15 this deficit in interference control in language highlights the fact that stimulant drugs
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17 acting on the catecholaminergic synapses in brain areas have a variety of effects on
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19 regulating and controlling executive processes. In an attempt to rule out other possible
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21 accounts of our results, we included screening of participants for several psychiatric
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23 disorders (schizophrenia, attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder, or obsessive-
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25 compulsive disorder) that have been associated with dopaminergic alterations (Davis,
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27 Kahn, Ko, & Davidson, 1991; Pooley, Fineberg, & Harrison, 2007; Tripp & Wickens,
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29 2008) and other preexisting psychiatric disorders, which are known to affect response
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31 inhibition (Rosenberg, Dick, O'Hearn, & Sweeney, 1997; Schachar & Logan, 1990;
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33 Thoma, Wiebel, & Daum, 2007) by using the MINI. However, it is important to note
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35 that the results of our study for the recreational cocaine polydrug users do not allow us
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37 to completely exclude the possibility of their deficit accounted in terms of preexistent
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39 underlying neurocognitive endophenotypes for stimulant drug addiction that could
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41 contribute to task performance (Ersche et al., 2012; Verdejo-García et al., 2008),
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43 although the presence of impairment for both chronic and recreational users with wide
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45 social and personal profiles lead us to consider that the use of cocaine—even for
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47 recreational purposes—caused the observed impairment of the inhibitory mechanisms
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49 that control verbal responses over and above differences in personal and social profiles.
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51 Another limitation of our study is the high rate of other drugs used by the recreational
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3 cocaine polydrug users (Groves, Kelly, & Parsons, 2009), making it difficult to
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5 distinguish the cognitive alterations produced by cocaine abuse itself from the use of
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7 other drugs. Similarly, we should note that there was a significant difference in the use
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9 of tobacco, alcohol, and cannabis between the groups that could also influence the
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11 difference in the obtained results. To try to control for these differences, we screened
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13 and selected participants whose predominant use of other drugs was cocaine, avoiding
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15 users of other stimulant drugs. The selection was based on self-reported measures of
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17 drug abuse that have been proved to strongly correlate with objective measures of drug
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19 abuse (Glintborg, Olsen, Poulsen, Linnet, & Dalhoff, 2008; Zaldívar Basurto et al.,
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21 2009). Because participants in both experiments reported very low use of cannabis and
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23 MDMA, and they were not users of other drugs, we think that our results cannot be
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25 attributed to the use of any other drugs. In addition, the abuse of these substances and
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27 their role in impaired executive functions have led to conflicting and inconsistent results
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29 (see Crean, Crane, & Mason, 2011; Kalechstein, Ii, Iii, Fantegrossi, & Newton, 2007;
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31 Verdejo-García, López-Torrecillas, Aguilar de Arcos, & Pérez-García, 2005). In this
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33 line, it is important to consider that cocaine and alcohol are often consumed together,
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35 and this is not an exception in our study. Given the fact that acute alcohol use impairs
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37 inhibitory control (Fillmore, 2007; Fillmore & Vogel-Sprott, 2000; Noël, Tomberg,
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39 Verbanck, & Campanella, 2010), it is difficult to determine whether the obtained effects
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41 are the result of cocaine use, alcohol use, or the use of both together (Jatlow et al.,
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43 1996). We tried to minimize the impact of long-term alcohol use by selecting samples
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45 who reported long-term alcohol intake below the criteria for high alcohol use (280
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47 g/week for men and 168g/week for women).
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52 In addition, although participants in Experiment 1 were undergoing regular urine
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54 toxicology screening as part of the treatment, some participants in Experiment 2 may
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3 have actively used either alcohol or cocaine within 24 to 48 hours prior to the
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5 experimental session, potentially affecting their performance on the picture-word task.
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7 Although this conclusion should be treated with caution, the fact that the impairment
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9 appeared in both recreational and chronic users (urine tested) suggests that this might
10
11 not have been the case.
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14 Despite these limitations and suggestions for further research, our study clearly
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16 indicates that the use of high and low amounts of cocaine could have an impact on the
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18 control of verbal interference during the production of speech. In summary, the results
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20 found in chronic and recreational cocaine users support the broader notion that cocaine
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22 use may impair the mechanism responsible for the intentional inhibition of distracting
23
24 information during spoken word production. This deficit can be translated to poor
25
26 efficacy in avoiding irrelevant information, causing errors and slower responses during
27
28 the production of utterances and other real-life situations in which the avoiding of
29
30 interference is mandatory.
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37 research
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TABLES

Table 1

Demographic Characteristics and Self-Reported Use of Cocaine and Other Psychoactive Drugs in Experiments 1 and 2

Sample	Experiment 1		Experiment 2	
	Chronic cocaine users	Cocaine-free controls	Recreational cocaine polydrug users	Cocaine-free controls
N (M:F) ^a	20 (18:2)	20 (15:5)	20 (13:7)	20 (8:12)
Age (years) ^a	32.6 (4.7)	30.4 (6.3)	24.4 (3.3)	23.6 (4.3)
Raven IQ ^a	103.5 (4.9)	106.5 (6.7)	104 (8.2)	103.5 (9.3)
Cigarettes (unit/day)	11.8 (7.5) ^{**}	1.65 (2.8)	8.55 (6.6) ^{**}	1.65 (3)
Alcohol (units/weeks)	30.8 (22.8) ^{**}	4.7 (4.1)	19.1 (13.6) ^{**}	5.4 (5.2)
Monthly Cannabis (joints)	3.2 (7.2) ^a	1 (1.8)	19.2 (22.5) ^{**}	1.6 (5.4)
MDMA (grams/last 6 months)	0.3 (1.45) ^a	0	1.6 (2) ^{**}	0
Years using cocaine	9.6 (4.8)	0	4.7 (3.5)	0
Monthly exposure (grams of cocaine)	15.4 (15.4)	0	4.5 (4.4)	0
Maximum amount in a 12-h period (grams)	2.9 (1.6)	0	1.4 (1)	0
Mean months of abstinence	4.25 (4)	0	0.6 (0.7)	0
Monthly money spent (EUR)	924 (926)	0	110 (94)	0

Note. Raven IQ: IQ measured by means of the Raven's Standard Progressive Matrices.

* $p < .05$, significant group difference; ** $p < .01$, significant group difference;

^aNo significant difference.

^bUnit is equivalent to 10 ml or 8 g of pure ethanol (International Center for Alcohol Policies, 2005; Spanish Ministry of Health, 2007; International Center for Alcohol, 2005). Chronic cocaine users are alcohol abstinent once they are engaged in the rehabilitation program.

Table 2

Mean Scores of Neuropsychological Test Performance in Experiments 1 and 2

Test	Experiment 1		Experiment 2	
	Chronic cocaine users	Cocaine-free controls	Recreational cocaine users	Cocaine-free controls
BNT ^a	50.1 (5.1)	50.4 (5.8)	50.3 (3.7)	49.8 (8)
VFT ^a	41.2 (5.5)	44.7 (7.64)	41.5 (12.2)	44.1 (7.6)
MST ^a	2.8 (0.9)	3.3 (0.6)	2.9 (0.8)	3.4 (1)

Note. BNT: Boston naming test; VF: verbal fluency test; MST: memory span test.

^aNonsignificant difference.

FIGURES

Figure 1

Or Peer Review

Figure 2

Peer Review

Figure 3

Figure 4

Review

Figure 5

Peer Review

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Figure 6

FIGURES CAPTIONS

Figure 1. Example of a semantically unrelated picture-word stimulus (a) and a semantically related stimulus (b).

Figure 2. Mean response latencies (in milliseconds) by conditions in Experiment 1.

Figure 3. Scatter diagram of the partial correlation of the picture-word effect and times per week using cocaine (residuals) in Experiment 1, controlling for the use of other drugs.

Figure 4. Scatter diagram of the partial correlation of the picture-word effect and amount of cocaine used (grams) in a week (residuals) in Experiment 1, controlling for the use of other drugs.

Figure 5. Mean response latencies (in milliseconds) by conditions in Experiment 2.

Figure 6. Scatter diagram of the partial correlation of the picture-word effect and times per month using cocaine (residuals) in Experiment 2, controlling for the use of other drugs.